

EFFECT OF ACADEMIC ENVIRONMENT, RELATIONSHIP, ON SES AND FAMILY ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND PERSONALITY OF 10TH CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract

The main aim of the present study was to explore the effect of family relationship, academic climate and SES on academic achievement and personality of high school students. Adolescent period is a crucial factor in building the personality and preparation for great kind of achievement. Family and school environment strongly affect it. Hence it was hypothesized that family relationship academic climate and, SES will significantly affect academic achievement and personality of high school students. 180 students of Sangli and Kolhapur district were selected by random sampling method 2x2x3 factorial research design was employed. Three way ANOVA was used to analyze the data. The findings of the study revealed that these three variables strongly and significantly affect academic achievement and personality of high school students most important finding of this study is that middle class family emerged as a most significant group when Scheffe's post-hoc comparison test was used.

Key words: *Academic environment, Family relationship, SES and academic achievement and personality.*

Family component has been a key them in children's education for more than three decades (Fantuzzo, Tighe and Childs 2000). In other words, family is the most essential factor for any development process of ant person. It influences our personality, attitude, thoughts and beliefs, social skill and achievements. Stephen J. Ceci and his colleagues (1997) propose that family relationships or parent -child interactions are the force that lead to academic performance. Children who are successful and well developed came from families where positive relationship existed between them and their parents, whereas children, who are discouraged and rejected at home, have lack of concentration in school work; fail to get success in academic achievement (Bowlby, 1967). Several other researchers concluded that, what happens in the system of family relationships has an important and statistically significant association with children's school success.

(Epstein, 1889, 1991, 1996; Hoover Dempsey and Sandler, 1997; Ketsetzix et. al., 1998; Rayan and Adams, 1995). Ara (1986) found that parents-child relationships and parent's personality was vstrongly associated with their adolescents children's personality.

High school students spend most of their time in attending school and doing home work. School environment or academic climate strongly contributes to the academic achievement and development of personality of adolescents (Greenbaum 1974). Academic climate in school influences overall development through academic demands. Of formal curricula and through exposure to teachers who emphasize academic achievement (Newman and Newman 1986). Perry (1908), the first educational leader, strongly stated that school climate significantly affects the student's academic performance. The systematic study of school climate (Anderson, 1982; Purkey and Smith, 1983; Creemers and Reezigt, 1999) has shown it's effectiveness in educational world. In addition, a series of studies have

shown that academic climate is directly related to academic achievement (Brookovers, et. al 1977; Briikover, 1978; Brookover and Lezotte, 1979; Rutter, et. al. 1979; Edmonds, 1979; Madaus, Airusian and Kellaghan, 1980; Shipman, 1981; Rutter, 1983; Good and Weinstein, 1986; Gottfredson and Gottfredson, 1989; Griffth, 1995; Freiberg, 1999). There is a no single definition of academic climate. Educators and researchers have recognized that there are complex sets of elements that make up academic climate, such elements are environmental, structural, safety, teaching and learning, relationship, various activities, moral, norms etc. (Cohen, 2006; Freiburg, 1999) as well as academic climate among school includes relationships among and between administration, teachers, parents, students and the community (Paliwal et. al., 2006) the vast majority of researchers suggest that academic climate reflects subjective experience (Cohen, 2006). Safe, caring, participatory and responsive school climate tends to foster grate attachment to school as well as to providing the optional foundation for academic performance (Blum, et. al., 2002; Osterman, 2000).

The socioeconomic status has been conceptualized ‘as a position’ in a society or a group and it is a cluster of factors, which includes occupation, income and cultural features of home (Sharma and et. al., 2005). Kuppuswamy (1980) considered education. Occupation and income as the important factors to determine the socioeconomic status of family. Higher the socioeconomic status the better the family environment which leads to healthy development of children’s personality (Madhu Bala, 2001). Alam Md. M. (2009) found that socio-economic status and academic achievement of the students is positively related with each other. Such positive relation is also found by Holmquist (1993).

High academic achievement and attractive personality is the urgent need of the 21st century. These are two sides of coin. Allport (1937) has defined personality as a dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determines his unique adjustment to his environment. According to good (1993) academic achievement means knowledge attained or skills developed in the school subjects. It is well known that, personality plays an important role in determining not only the behavior of an individual but also his overall success (Manju Megata and et. al., 2008). According to Cattell (1950) the personality of an individual is that which enables us to predict what he will do in given situation. Keeping this fact in mind the present study was designed to see interlinking system among variables underling the study.

Aim of the study:

Family plays a crucial role in personality, educational progress, social and emotional maturity and career development of adolescents, but in present study only personality and educational development is considered. Main aim of the present study is to examine the effect of parental attitudes (acceptance) on personality and academic achievement of high school student.

Objectives

- To find out the effects of family relation, academic climate and SES on personality traits such as reserved – warmhearted, obedient – assertive and shy venturesome of high school student.
- To investigate the influence of family relation, academic climate and SES on academic achievement of high school students.

Hypotheses :

- Family relation, academic climate and SES will interact to yield different outcomes of personality traits such as reserved – warmhearted, obedient – assertive and shy – venturesome of high school students.
- Family relation, academic climate and SES will interact to yield different outcomes of academic achievement of high school student.

Method :**Sample –**

The hundred students studying in the 10 class from various high schools in Sangli and Kolhapur city were selected by random sampling method. They varied in age range from 14 to 15 years. The ratio of Upper, Middle and Lower class SES was kept as 1:1:1 out of 180 students only 150 student were taken into consideration of analysis of the data.

Tools –

Research was conducted using the following psychological tests.

1) Family Relationship Inventory (FRI) –

This inventory is prepared by Sherry and Sinha (1987) on the basis of Brunken and Crites's Family Relationship Inventory in the Indian situation. The inventory is intended to identify the individuals who feel emotionally accepted. Over protected or rejected by their parents. However in the present study, only acceptance tendency is considered. FRI includes 150 items with true/false alternatives. Inventory has high reliability and validity. A high score in each area shows high degree of one's feeling of being accepted, concentrated and avoided by parents.

2) Academic Climate Description Questionnaire (ACDQ):

ACDQ is developed by Shah and Shah (1988). It consists 84 items based on four dimensions viz. physical material, interpersonal trust, school provisions and Academic provision the reliability of ACDQ is 85 and validity is quite high. A high score shows high academic climate while low score shows low academic climate.

3) Socio-economic Status Scale (SESS) :

This scale constructed by R. L. Bharadwaj (1984). It is based on seven areas and respondents have to put only tick mark on related information. Higher and lower score on this scale indicated respectively upper and lower socio-economic status.

4) High school Personality Questionnaire (HSPQ) :

The questionnaire published by institute for personality and ability testing (IPAT). The HSPQ measures fourteen distinct traits of personality, instead of all the 14 factor only three factors were considered viz reserved warm hearted, obedient – assertive and shy-venturesome which was supposed to be most relevant to the study.

5) Academic Achievement Score :

Academic achievement is usually defined in three ways – the grades earned in school, student's performance and score achieved on standardized test of academic achievement. In the present study for the consideration of academic achievement score of 10th class, student among upper, middle and lower class, the percentage of their previous year final examination and percentage of current year examination were collected. The total of these two scores of each subject was converted into an average percentage score.

Design of the Study :

2 X 2 X 3 Factorial research design was employed for the present study. Personality and academic achievement are dependent variables. Family relationships are independent variables, which were studied at two levels, viz high and low. Academic climate (high and low) and SES (upper, middle and lower class) was other independent variables. Three-way ANOVA was separately done for studying personality and academic achievement. Finally Scheffe's post-hoc comparison was done.

Procedure :

The headmasters of the various school were contacted and permission was sought from them to conduct a research on their students. After seeking permission psychological tests were administered one by one with a short rest in a group of 25 to 30 students at a time. Annual percentage of marks for their previous year examination was collected from school records. At last after six months when the result of 10th class was announced annual percentage of mark for their current year examination was collected.

Table No. 1**Summary of Three Way ANOVA on personality Traits of High School Student**

Personality Traits	Source of Variance	FRI	AcCL	SES	FRI X AcCL	FRI X SES	SES X AcCL	FRI X AcCL X SES	Error	Total
P1	Sum of Squares	39.20	13.89	1063.54	22.76	18.90	12.21	4.41	288.0	9060
	Df	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	168	180
	Mean Squares	39.20	13.89	531.77	22.76	9.45	6.11	2.21	1.36	
	F	28.88*	10.23*	391.83*	16.77*	6.96**	4.50*	1.63		
P2	Sum of Squares	40.14	2.45	980.08	4.67	24.34	9.10	7.54	201.73	9045.0
	Df	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	168	180
	Mean Squares	40.14	2.45	490.04	4.67	12.17	4.55	3.77	1.20	
	F	33.43*	2.04	408.10*	3.89**	10.14*	3.79	3.14		
P3	Sum of Squares	28.01	18.05	972.98	9.34	38.71	5.73	10.18	173.73	9431.00
	df	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	168	180
	Mean Squares	28.01	18.05	486.49	9.34	19.36	2.87	5.09	1.03	
	F	27.08*	17.45*	470.43*	9.03**	18.72*	2.77	4.92*		

* Significant at 0.05 Level

** Significant at 0.01 Level

Results and Discussion:

Table No. 1 reveals that F ratios for the difference in means of personality traits such as 'Reserved – Warmhearted', 'Obedient – Assertive' and 'Shy-Venturesome' scores for family relationships was found to be

significant at 0.01 level of confidence. It shows that high and low tendency of acceptance of family relationships yield different outcomes of above personality traits. Family relations are strongly affected to personality characteristics. Parent-child relations in the early life play a crucial role in the personality development process of children. Parents having acceptance attitude towards their children, encourage them to fulfill their potentialities (Sheri and Sinha 1997). It could be seen that academic climate has a significant effect on ‘reserved – warmhearted’ and ‘shy venturesome’ personality traits. F ratio (10.23 and 17.45) are significant at 0.01 alpha level. Academic climate significantly contributes in development of personality of adolescents (Greenbaum 1947). High academic climate of school includes the variety of extracurricular activities and supportive staff, which are benefits to the student to develop their personality. It is also inferred that all the F ratios for SES was significant at 0.01 level of confidence. It shows that upper, middle and lower SES yielded different outcomes of personality traits among high school students. Parents from upper and lower SES spend comparatively less time which their children than middle SES parents; therefore these children were either emotionally neglected or over protected. On the country middle class parents were aware of emotions, needs, demands and potentials of their children. Hence these children become assertive, venturesome and warmhearted. Table 1 shows that, F ratio for two way interaction of family relationships and academic climate as well as family relationships and SES were found to be significant. While F ration for three-way interaction was found to be significant only for ‘Shy-Venturesome’ personality traits.

Table No. 2

Summary of Three-way ANOVA on Academic Achievement score of High School Student.

Source if Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Family Relationship	1227.2	1	1227.22	38.05*
Academic Climate	2538.76	1	2538.76	78.72*
SES	21333.88	2	10666.93	330.77*
FR X Academic Climate	142.22	1	142.22	4.41**
FR X SES	1491.41	2	745.70	23.12**
Academic Climate X SES	1327.68	2	663.83	20.59*
FR X Climate X SES	233.21	2	116.60	3.61
Error	5417.87	168	32.24	
Total	1152988.00	180		
* Significant at 0.01 Level. ** Significant at 0.05 Level				

It may be observed from table No. 2 that the F ratios for the difference in means of academic achievement score for students belonging to high and low family relationships groups was found to be significant at 0.01 level of confidence. F ratios for the difference in means of academic achievement of high and low academic climate groups was also found to be significant at 0.01 level of alpha. School climate is significant correlated with pupil’s academic achievement (Emmer et. al. 1979). School climate promotes the student’s ability to learn properly; hence their academic achievement is increased (Ghaith 2003, Kerr 2004 and Finnan, et. al.2003). it could be also seen from table no. 2 that F ratio for SES was found to be significant at 0.01 level. It shows that upper, middle and lower SES yielded different outcomes of academic achievement. Anita Sharma and her colleagues (2005) found that SES

significantly affect to children's academic achievement, Sing C.P. (1981) found that SES is positively and significantly correlated with academic achievement. F ratio for all tow-way interaction effect was found to be significant, hence hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Table No. 3
Scheffe's test of Post Hoc Comparison for dependent variables.

SES	Academic Achievement			Reserved Warmhearted			Obedient Assertive			Shy Venturesome			
	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05			Subset For Alpha = 0.05			Subset for alpha = 0.05			Subset for alpha = 0.05		
		1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Lower SES	60	6.48			3.18			3.35			3.51		
Upper SES	60		78.93			7.48			7.56			7.78	
Middle SES	60			92.15			8.90			8.80			8.91

All mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 3 depicts the picture of post hoc comparison made on dependent variables by Scheffe's test. It could be clearly seen from table that lower class students have o lowest mean on all the dependent variables viz. 65.45, 3.18, 3.35 and 3.51 respectively on academic achievement, reserved-warmhearted, obedient – assertive and shy venturesome. While middle class family students have a highest mean score on academic achievement (92.15), reserved warmhearted (8.90), obedient assertive (8.80) and shy venturesome (8.91). Most important fact is that all the mean difference is significant on 0.05 level. Hence middle class family is the most significant group in this research.

Conclusions

The findings of the study revealed that family relationships, academic climate and SES have a strong and significant effect on personality and academic achievement of high school students. Moreover two-way interactions of these three variables were also affecting to personality and academic achievement. Most important finding of this study is that, middle class family emerged as a most significant group.

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